

From Post-Quantum Cryptography to Quantum DevSecOps: Securing the Quantum Software Lifecycle

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Abstract—Quantum security is often framed as post-quantum cryptography. This article argues that quantum software also needs secure engineering lifecycles. Using SecQDevOps as a reference case, we outline how Quantum DevSecOps connects coding, compilation, testing, monitoring, compliance, and evidence generation to support trustworthy quantum software development.

Index Terms—Quantum DevSecOps, quantum software assurance, secure software development lifecycle, quantum machine learning operations, Internet of Quantum Things, compliance automation, security evidence.

Quantum computing is changing the way security professionals think about the long-term protection of digital systems. The most visible part of this discussion is post-quantum cryptography, where public-key algorithms that may be vulnerable to future cryptographically relevant quantum computers are replaced by algorithms designed to resist such attacks. This migration is necessary and has become more concrete with the publication of the first post-quantum cryptography standards [1]. It addresses only part of the quantum-security problem. It protects classical systems against future quantum-enabled cryptanalysis, but it does not secure the lifecycle of quantum applications themselves.

Quantum software is no longer only a theoretical description of algorithms. It is implemented through programming frameworks, circuit descriptions, hybrid quantum-classical workflows, compilers, simulators, cloud backends, optimisation routines, machine-learning pipelines, and operational interfaces. A developer may write code in a high-level quantum framework, pass it through transpilation and compilation, test it on simulators, execute it through a remote backend, and integrate the result into a larger classical system. Each step introduces assumptions, dependencies, configuration choices,

and possible security weaknesses. The resulting application is therefore a software supply chain, not only a quantum algorithm.

Conventional DevSecOps practices provide continuous integration, automated testing, dependency scanning, secret detection, release automation, deployment controls, and runtime monitoring. These practices remain necessary, but they do not fully cover quantum-specific artefacts and transformations. A conventional pipeline may identify an unsafe dependency, but it may not record whether a quantum circuit was transformed correctly, whether a backend assumption was valid, whether a compiler warning affected a release decision, or whether a quantum machine-learning model can be traced back to its dataset, circuit configuration, and evaluation evidence.

This gap matters because quantum software is beginning to intersect with domains where informal engineering practices are unacceptable. Open-source quantum frameworks require vulnerability handling and maintainable releases. Quantum machine-learning workflows in medical or scientific settings require reproducibility, traceability, and controlled data handling. Quantum optimisation for energy systems and other critical infrastructures requires authenticated inputs, bounded execution, interpretable outputs, and operational fallback. Distributed testing environments require node enrolment, sandboxing, telemetry, and incident evidence.

A Quantum DevSecOps approach treats quantum software as a lifecycle assurance problem. It combines secure coding, quantum-aware compilation, emulator-first testing, policy-based release gates, controlled deployment, runtime monitoring, and evidence management. Trust should be accumulated throughout the lifecycle rather than asserted at the end. A release should be considered trustworthy only when relevant artefacts and decisions can be inspected, including source versions, dependencies, circuits, compiler reports, test results, compliance decisions, signed packages, deployment manifests, telemetry, incident records, and drift reports.

SecQDevOps offers a public reference case for this direction. Its public description frames the project around a secure continuous DevOps pipeline for quantum software and hardware development, combining high-level quantum programming languages, secure hardware-aware compilers, automated security assessment, real-time vulnerability detection, and IoQT-based collaborative testing [2]. The value of the reference case is that it makes the required integration

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visible across quantum development environments, secure compilation, Quantum MLOps, AI-driven security services, distributed testing, compliance, certification, and operational evidence.

The position developed here is that quantum security must expand from post-quantum cryptographic migration to secure quantum software engineering. Without this shift, experimental habits such as undocumented notebooks, manual backend choices, weak dependency control, incomplete testing, and unverifiable claims of security or compliance may carry over into production systems. Evidence-driven Quantum DevSecOps can help quantum software mature before it becomes embedded in critical services.

I. THE QUANTUM SOFTWARE ASSURANCE PROBLEM

Quantum security is often framed as a cryptographic migration problem. Classical systems must replace algorithms that may be broken by future quantum computers with post-quantum alternatives. This transition is necessary, but it does not address the security of quantum software itself. As quantum applications move from laboratory examples to cloud services, hybrid workflows, and domain-specific pilots, they will need the engineering discipline expected from other security-critical software. The question is no longer only whether classical cryptography can survive quantum attacks. It is also whether quantum software can be developed, compiled, tested, deployed, monitored, and audited in a trustworthy way.

A. Quantum Applications Are Not Just Algorithms

A practical quantum application is rarely an isolated mathematical object. It is usually implemented through a chain of software artefacts and services, including source code written in frameworks such as Qiskit [3] or Qrisp [4], circuit descriptions, classical pre-processing logic, transpilation steps, compiler optimisations, simulator runs, backend selection, cloud execution, result post-processing, and release packaging.

Each step introduces assumptions, dependencies, configuration choices, and possible failure modes. A source-level change may alter the generated circuit. A transpiler setting may affect the executed representation. A backend choice may influence the reliability of the result. A dataset split or model parameter may change the behaviour of a hybrid quantum-classical workflow. The resulting system is better understood as a software supply chain than as a single quantum algorithm.

B. Hybrid Workflows Expand the Assurance Boundary

Most near-term quantum applications are hybrid quantum-classical systems. Classical software prepares data, controls optimisation loops, invokes quantum routines, interprets measurement results, and integrates the output into a larger application. The quantum component may be a circuit, a variational layer, a sampling procedure, an optimisation kernel, or a quantum-enhanced model.

This hybrid structure expands the assurance boundary. A security assessment that focuses only on the quantum circuit will miss vulnerabilities in orchestration logic, dependency

management, access credentials, backend APIs, dataset handling, model packaging, or release decisions. Conversely, a conventional software scan may detect vulnerable Python packages but say little about whether a circuit transformation preserved the intended computation or whether a backend-specific assumption was documented. Quantum software assurance must cover both the classical and quantum parts of the workflow and the interfaces between them.

C. NISQ Execution Makes Reproducibility a Security Concern

The current Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) context makes assurance more difficult. Execution can be affected by noise, calibration drift, qubit connectivity, gate errors, measurement choices, simulator assumptions, and backend availability. Earlier work on Quantum DevOps framed NISQ-era quantum development as a lifecycle process involving development, testing, deployment, execution, monitoring, and feedback rather than a one-time implementation step [5].

This lifecycle view has direct security implications. If an organisation cannot reconstruct why a workflow produced a result, it cannot distinguish normal hardware variability from poor configuration, implementation error, insecure orchestration, or adversarial manipulation. Reproducibility, therefore, becomes part of the security posture. A quantum software pipeline should preserve the code version, dependency state, circuit configuration, transpiler and compiler settings, simulator or backend metadata, dataset references, model parameters where relevant, execution logs, test outcomes, and release decisions. These records are not only useful for debugging. They provide the basis for auditability, incident analysis, compliance assessment, and justified trust claims.

D. Classical DevSecOps Leaves Quantum-Specific Gaps

Classical DevSecOps provides a useful starting point. Continuous integration, automated testing, static analysis, dependency scanning, container security, deployment automation, monitoring, and incident response remain necessary. They are not sufficient on their own. Classical DevSecOps tools do not normally understand quantum-specific artefacts such as circuits, transpilation outputs, quantum intermediate representations, noise-aware simulation settings, backend constraints, or quantum machine-learning lineage. Without additional controls, the classical parts of the pipeline may be well governed while the quantum-specific transformations remain weakly documented and only partially checked.

The gap becomes more visible when large language models are introduced into development workflows. LLMs can support code generation, test creation, documentation, and vulnerability triage. They may also generate insecure code, incorrect explanations, fragile tests, or plausible but invalid fixes. In quantum software, where the developer community and tooling are still maturing, such outputs should be treated as untrusted contributions until checked by conventional and quantum-aware controls. Security-relevant prompts, generated artefacts, modifications, review decisions, and accepted outputs should be traceable when they affect the codebase or release evidence.

E. From Secure Code to Assured Pipelines

Secure code is necessary, but quantum software also needs assurance over how code is transformed, tested, released, deployed, and monitored. A mature pipeline should answer concrete questions about which version was built, which dependencies and quantum artefacts were included, which compiler transformed the programme, which backend was selected, which tests were executed, which findings were remediated or waived, and which evidence supports the release decision.

The quantum software ecosystem is still young enough for these practices to be built in early. Otherwise, experimental habits such as undocumented notebooks, manual backend choices, informal testing, weak dependency control, and unverifiable security claims may carry over into production environments. Quantum DevSecOps should therefore be understood as a lifecycle assurance discipline that combines secure coding, quantum-aware compilation, emulator-first testing, policy-based gates, runtime monitoring, and auditable evidence.

II. REGULATION, STANDARDS, AND WHAT EXISTING APPROACHES MISS

Quantum software assurance is not only a technical concern. It is also shaped by regulatory, operational, and sector-specific expectations. A quantum workflow used for experimentation may tolerate manual checks and incomplete documentation. A quantum workflow used in open-source infrastructure, medical analysis, energy optimisation, or critical-service support cannot rely on the same informal process. It must support traceability, risk management, evidence generation, vulnerability handling, and controlled release decisions.

A. Regulatory Pressure on Quantum Software

European cybersecurity and digital regulation increasingly treat software as a lifecycle responsibility. The Cyber Resilience Act establishes horizontal cybersecurity requirements for products with digital elements, including secure design, vulnerability handling, documentation, and market-facing security obligations [6]. Although the regulation does not define a separate category for quantum software, hybrid quantum-classical tools, quantum software development kits, cloud-connected quantum services, and packaged quantum applications may fall within its logic when they are provided as digital products or components.

NIS2 adds an operational perspective. It requires covered entities to apply appropriate and proportionate technical, operational, and organisational measures for cybersecurity risk management, including incident handling, business continuity, supply-chain security, vulnerability management, and cryptography [7]. For quantum software used by essential entities, this points beyond code correctness. It implies monitored operation, dependency control, incident evidence, and management-level accountability.

The AI Act becomes relevant where quantum components are embedded in AI systems, especially in quantum machine-learning workflows. Its requirements for high-risk AI systems

include risk management, data governance, technical documentation, logging, transparency, human oversight, accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity [8]. A quantum-enhanced model used in a regulated context therefore needs evidence about data provenance, model lineage, evaluation results, robustness assumptions, release controls, and the quantum component itself.

ALTAI complements this legal framing as a voluntary self-assessment checklist for trustworthy AI [9]. For quantum machine-learning workflows, it can translate broad governance principles into practical evidence requirements for model lineage, data governance, robustness checks, human review, and accountability. The GDPR is also relevant whenever quantum workflows process personal data, including many medical, scientific, and telemetry use cases [10]. A Quantum DevSecOps pipeline should therefore preserve evidence of data flows, access controls, retention rules, pseudonymisation or anonymisation choices, and the lawful basis for processing.

The wider policy landscape is evolving. The European Commission identifies quantum technologies as strategically important for technological sovereignty, industrial capacity, supply-chain resilience, and governance. The future EU Quantum Act is scheduled for adoption in 2026 and is expected to address research and innovation, industrial scale-up, and supply-chain resilience [11]. This reinforces the need for assurance methods that connect quantum engineering decisions with compliance evidence.

B. Sector Standards Add Concrete Constraints

Sector-specific standards make these obligations more concrete. In medical software, assurance is linked to controlled development, risk management, validation, safe maintenance, data protection, traceability, and reproducibility. A quantum machine-learning workflow applied to medical images must preserve dataset references, model parameters, evaluation metrics, baseline comparisons, release decisions, and the evidence needed for technical review. The use of anonymised or de-identified data does not remove the need for access control, data minimisation, and auditable processing.

Energy systems introduce a different constraint set. Grid operation depends on timely, reliable, and secure optimisation under physical, economic, and operational constraints. A quantum optimisation component cannot be treated as an isolated solver. It must be connected to authenticated data sources, validated input formats, bounded execution times, interpretable outputs, cybersecurity controls, and operational fallback logic. In such contexts, a security failure may affect software integrity and continuity of service.

C. Limits of Current Approaches

Several approaches contribute to quantum-era security, but none is sufficient alone. Post-quantum cryptography protects classical systems against future quantum-enabled cryptanalysis, but it does not govern how quantum software is built or operated. Classical DevSecOps provides mature practices for continuous integration, testing, scanning, deployment, and monitoring, but it does not natively handle quantum artefacts.

TABLE I
APPROACHES TO QUANTUM-ERA SECURITY AND THEIR ASSURANCE
LIMITS.

Approach	Contribution	Limit
Post-quantum cryptography	Protects classical systems against quantum-enabled cryptanalytic attacks.	Does not secure the lifecycle of quantum software, compilers, workflows, or releases.
Classical DevSecOps	Provides CI/CD automation, testing, scanning, deployment controls, and monitoring.	Does not natively represent circuits, transpilation outputs, backend constraints, or QML lineage.
Quantum programming frameworks	Enable developers to express quantum algorithms and hybrid workflows.	Usually focus on functionality and execution rather than security gates, compliance, and audit evidence.
Quantum DevSecOps	Integrates quantum-aware controls across coding, compilation, testing, release, deployment, and monitoring.	Still requires mature standards, benchmarks, evidence schemas, and industrial validation.

Quantum programming frameworks enable development, but they are not complete assurance environments. Quantum DevSecOps addresses the missing integration layer by connecting secure coding, compilation, testing, release gates, runtime monitoring, compliance, and evidence.

D. Implication for Secure Quantum Development

The resulting requirement is clear. Quantum software assurance must be lifecycle-based and evidence-driven. A secure workflow should not only execute tests or produce a dashboard. It should preserve the artefacts needed to justify decisions, including threat models, security requirements, software and quantum bills of materials, compiler reports, test traces, compliance snapshots, signed release records, deployment manifests, telemetry, incident logs, and drift reports. This evidence-oriented model connects technical controls with governance, accountability, auditability, and release assurance.

III. SECQDEVOPS AS A QUANTUM DEVSECOPS REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

SecQDevOps is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action focused on secure continuous development for quantum technologies. Its public description frames the project around a secure DevOps pipeline for quantum software and hardware development, combining high-level quantum programming languages, secure hardware-aware compilers, automated security assessments, real-time vulnerability detection, and IoQT-based collaborative testing [2]. This public description provides a reference case for examining Quantum DevSecOps as an end-to-end assurance workflow rather than as a set of isolated tools.

A practical Quantum DevSecOps architecture must connect secure quantum programming, hardware-aware compilation, quantum machine-learning operations, controlled testing, AI-assisted security analysis, compliance, certification, deployment, and monitoring. The objective is not to add one more scanner to an existing pipeline. It is to create a workflow

in which each stage produces inputs for the next stage and evidence for later inspection.

A. Architecture Overview

The high-level architecture in Fig. 1 shows how these capabilities fit together. It links quantum software development environments, secure hardware-aware compilers, Quantum MLOps, AI-driven security services, distributed IoQT platforms, compliance and certification mechanisms, and DevOps pipeline integration. The figure should be read as an assurance architecture. Its purpose is to show where controls, evidence, and decisions must be connected across the lifecycle.

B. Secure Development and Hardware-Aware Compilation

The development layer is the entry point for quantum and hybrid quantum-classical software. It must support ordinary secure software engineering practices, including code review, dependency checking, secret detection, static analysis, test automation, and review of generated code. It must also support quantum-specific controls for unsafe circuit construction, undocumented backend assumptions, insecure use of quantum libraries, fragile transpilation behaviour, and weak hybrid orchestration.

LLM-assisted development can be integrated at this layer, but generated code, tests, or explanations should be treated as untrusted contributions until validated. Where LLM outputs affect release-relevant artefacts, the prompt context, generated output, subsequent modification, review decision, and accepted artefact should be traceable.

Secure hardware-aware compilation is central because compilation is not a neutral step in quantum software. A compiler or transpiler may change the structure of a circuit, adapt it to a target backend, introduce optimisation choices, or map logical operations to hardware-specific constraints. A secure compiler should therefore produce not only compiled output but also a report recording inputs, transformations, warnings, assumptions, and target constraints. This report becomes part of the release evidence.

C. Quantum MLOps, AI Security, and IoQT Testing

Quantum MLOps is needed when quantum components are embedded into machine-learning workflows. Assurance must cover dataset references, feature preparation, model parameters, training configuration, evaluation metrics, baseline comparisons, model packaging, and deployment context. A secure process should preserve lineage between the dataset, code version, circuit configuration, training run, evaluation results, and released model artefact. It should also distinguish exploratory workflows from release-candidate workflows, where evidence completeness, policy compliance, signing, and approval become stricter.

AI-driven security services extend the architecture from development-time checks to continuous assessment. Predictive services can help prioritise risks and likely failure points, while anomaly detection and intrusion detection can monitor telemetry, traces, execution behaviour, and pipeline events.

Fig. 1. High-level SecQDevOps architecture for secure quantum software and hardware engineering. The architecture links quantum software development, secure hardware-aware compilation, quantum MLOps, AI-driven security services, distributed IoQT platforms, compliance and certification, and DevOps pipeline integration.

These outputs are most useful when linked to the relevant code version, release package, deployment manifest, and operational context.

The distributed IoQT layer provides controlled environments for testing quantum software across quantum-emulated or distributed execution nodes. In this setting, the assurance boundary includes node enrolment, trust records, job scheduling, sandbox isolation, trace generation, and test reporting. Each execution should produce enough information to reconstruct where it ran, under which configuration, and with which result. IoQT therefore acts as both a technical validation mechanism and an evidence-generation layer.

D. Compliance, Certification, and Pipeline Evidence

Compliance and certification must be embedded into the pipeline rather than appended after development. A release candidate should be evaluated against policy requirements, vulnerability findings, test outcomes, evidence completeness, signing requirements, and deployment constraints. The result should be an explicit gate decision such as pass, fail, or exception. Exceptions should be justified, time-bounded, and linked to responsible approval.

The DevOps pipeline provides the operational backbone for this process. During build, it captures provenance and dependency information. During compilation, it stores compiler reports. During testing, it stores traces and reports. During release, it produces signed packages and compliance snapshots. During deployment, it binds the release to a deployment manifest and environment baseline. During operation, it collects telemetry, alerts, incident actions, and drift reports.

This integration changes the meaning of trust. Trust is accumulated through controlled transformations, explicit decisions, reproducible evidence, and continuous monitoring. A working experiment may show that a workflow can execute. An assured pipeline shows what was executed, how it was transformed, which controls were applied, which risks remain, and why the result was allowed to proceed.

IV. SECURITY EVIDENCE AS THE MISSING LAYER

Security controls are useful only when their outcomes can be inspected, trusted, and acted upon. A pipeline that runs tests, scans dependencies, checks policies, and signs releases may still provide weak assurance if the results remain scattered across logs, build servers, dashboards, and manual reports. For quantum software, this problem is more serious because the lifecycle includes artefacts that are not yet well represented in conventional assurance practice. Circuits, transpilation outputs, backend assumptions, emulator traces, quantum machine-learning lineage, and distributed execution records must be treated as first-class evidence.

A. From Control Execution to Evidence Generation

A common weakness in security automation is the assumption that running a control is equivalent to producing assurance. The two are different. A scanner may run without its findings being linked to a release decision. A test may pass without recording the test environment. A compiler may generate an executable representation while losing the transformation assumptions. A deployment may succeed even though the deployed environment differs from the approved baseline.

Evidence-oriented assurance requires each control to produce a durable and context-rich artefact. The artefact should identify what was checked, which input was used, which tool or policy performed the check, which result was obtained, and how that result influenced the next decision. This does not mean storing every raw log indefinitely. It means preserving enough structured evidence to reconstruct the security-relevant path from source code to runtime behaviour.

In a quantum DevSecOps pipeline, the correctness or security of a release cannot be inferred from a successful build alone. The release decision must be supported by evidence that source code, dependencies, quantum artefacts, compiler outputs, tests, policies, signing, deployment targets, and run-

time assumptions were controlled within an acceptable risk boundary.

B. Lifecycle Evidence and Assurance Roles

The evidence model should follow the lifecycle. Planning should preserve threat models, risk registers, security requirements, and policy baselines. Development and build should preserve code-review records, static-analysis findings, dependency scans, secret-detection results, software bills of materials, build provenance, and attestations. For quantum software, a conventional software bill of materials is not enough. A quantum bill of materials can extend the idea by recording circuits, gate sets, framework versions, quantum libraries, transpilation settings, simulator configuration, backend assumptions, and quantum intermediate representations.

Compilation should produce a security-relevant report that records input representations, transformation steps, optimisation choices, target constraints, warnings, and assumptions. Testing should preserve unit-test results, integration-test results, emulator-based validation records, IoQT trace bundles, distributed execution reports, and exception records. Release and deployment should preserve compliance snapshots, gate decisions, waiver records, signed release packages, deployment manifests, and environment baselines. Operation should preserve telemetry, alert records, incident actions, compliance drift reports, cryptographic posture records, and key-rotation records.

Different stakeholders need different views of this evidence. Developers need actionable feedback about findings, failed tests, unsafe dependencies, and insecure coding patterns. Security teams need correlation across stages to determine whether a runtime alert is linked to a known vulnerability, configuration drift, or previous waiver. Operators need deployment and runtime context. Auditors and assessors need to reconstruct which controls were required, which controls were executed, which evidence was produced, and why a release was approved. Governance teams need aggregated views of exceptions, unresolved risks, compliance drift, and evidence completeness.

The same evidence store should support these roles without exposing unnecessary sensitive information. This requires access control, redaction, minimisation, and separation between raw operational data and audit-level summaries. In sensitive domains, such as medical workflows, evidence must support reproducibility and review without leaking protected data. Evidence design is therefore also a privacy and governance concern.

C. From Trust Claims to Auditability

Claims such as “secure”, “compliant”, or “quantum-safe” are weak unless they are tied to verifiable evidence. A stronger claim is more specific. A release was built from a known source version, with recorded dependencies, compiled under documented assumptions, tested in controlled environments, evaluated against defined policies, signed, deployed to a verified baseline, and monitored for drift and incidents.

This evidence-oriented model does not eliminate risk. It makes risk visible and governable. It allows a team to determine what is known, what is assumed, what has changed, and which residual risks remain. For quantum software, visibility matters because the ecosystem is still developing and many assurance practices are not yet standardised.

The practical goal is not to produce more paperwork. It is to make security decisions reproducible. A quantum DevSecOps pipeline should treat evidence as a core output of the lifecycle, alongside code, models, circuits, and deployment artefacts. Without such evidence, quantum software may execute successfully while remaining difficult to trust, certify, or operate responsibly.

V. PRACTICAL SCENARIOS

The need for Quantum DevSecOps becomes clearer when considered through concrete workflows. The following scenarios show how assurance requirements change across open-source development, medical quantum machine learning, energy-grid optimisation, and distributed IoQT testing. They differ in domain and risk profile, but they share the same principle. Quantum software should move towards release or operation only when the relevant artefacts, controls, decisions, and residual risks are visible.

A. Secure Open-Source Quantum Software

Assurance objective. An open-source quantum maintainer needs each contribution to pass conventional and quantum-aware security checks before release, so accepted code remains traceable, reviewable, and aligned with project security policy.

Open-source quantum software depends on public frameworks, libraries, examples, and community contributions. A contribution to a Qrisp- or Qiskit-based project may include new quantum routines, tests, documentation, or LLM-generated code. Such contributions should not be trusted only because they arrive through a familiar repository.

A secure workflow should combine conventional checks, including static analysis, dependency scanning, secret detection, licence checks, and generated-test review, with quantum-aware checks for unsafe circuit construction, undocumented backend assumptions, fragile transpilation behaviour, and insecure hybrid orchestration. If an LLM was used, the generated artefact should pass through the same gates as human-authored code. The release process should preserve findings, remediation actions, test results, dependency records, compiler or transpiler reports where applicable, and a compliance snapshot for the release candidate.

B. Medical-Domain Quantum MLOps

Assurance objective. A medical-domain model developer needs each quantum machine-learning experiment to preserve data references, model lineage, evaluation evidence, and release decisions so results can be reproduced and reviewed without exposing sensitive data.

Medical quantum machine-learning workflows require stricter controls than general experimentation. A hybrid

quantum-classical model for image-analysis research may involve approved or anonymised data, feature extraction, model training, baseline comparison, packaging, and release-candidate review. Each run should preserve the code version, dataset reference, data split, configuration parameters, circuit settings, model artefact, evaluation metrics, and release-related outputs.

The workflow should distinguish research mode from release-candidate mode. Research mode may allow rapid iteration, while release-candidate mode should enforce evidence completeness, baseline comparison, policy checks, signing, and explicit approval. Data boundaries must also be enforced. Sensitive raw data should not be copied, exposed, or moved outside the authorised processing scope, and evidence should support review without revealing protected data. For imbalanced medical datasets, the evidence package should include metrics that reveal behaviour on minority classes or clinically relevant rare patterns.

C. Energy-Grid Quantum Optimisation

Assurance objective. An energy-system operator needs quantum optimisation outputs to be produced from authenticated inputs, validated constraints, bounded execution times, and reviewable evidence so recommendations can support operational decisions without weakening grid resilience.

Energy-grid optimisation involves time-sensitive decisions under physical, economic, and security constraints. A quantum or hybrid optimisation component may support grid configuration, storage actions, generation scheduling, or balancing decisions. In operational settings, forecasts and constraints may be updated frequently, so the software must process inputs, formulate the problem, execute the solver, and return results within a bounded time window.

Security requirements are closely linked to reliability. Forecasts, grid topology, constraints, and operational parameters must come from authenticated sources and be validated before they influence optimisation. The evidence package should record the input format, constraint set, model formulation, execution configuration, output recommendation, timing information, and any triggered gate. If optimisation fails, exceeds the latency bound, or produces a result outside operational limits, the system should support fallback logic rather than silently returning an unsafe recommendation.

D. Distributed IoQT Testing

Assurance objective. A quantum software tester needs distributed IoQT jobs to run only on enrolled and isolated nodes, with traceable execution records, so failures can be diagnosed and test evidence can support later release decisions.

The Internet of Quantum Things extends assurance to distributed testing and simulation. Quantum software may be tested across multiple quantum-emulated nodes or distributed execution resources before using more constrained execution environments. The aim is to validate functionality, security assumptions, orchestration logic, and execution behaviour under controlled but heterogeneous conditions.

A distributed test should begin with node enrolment. Each participating node must have a trust record, known configuration, and authorised role. Jobs should run inside isolated execution boundaries so that one test cannot interfere with another, access unauthorised data, or misuse node resources. The pipeline should record where the job ran, which node participated, which configuration was used, which trace was produced, and which result was obtained. The evidence should help distinguish software defects, unavailable nodes, policy violations, sandbox restrictions, network conditions, and execution constraints.

Across these scenarios, Quantum DevSecOps is less about a single tool than about disciplined movement from experimentation to accountable engineering.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS AND OPEN CHALLENGES

Quantum DevSecOps should be understood as an extension of secure software engineering to a new class of hybrid systems, not as a specialised add-on for quantum experts. The following recommendations translate the preceding discussion into practical guidance for organisations that develop, integrate, or assess quantum software.

A. Treat Quantum Software as a Supply Chain

Quantum software should be governed as a supply chain of source code, dependencies, circuits, compiler outputs, datasets, models, execution environments, and operational evidence. This view forces teams to identify where artefacts originate, how they are transformed, which tools influence them, and which assumptions are carried into release or deployment.

It also clarifies ownership. Developers are responsible for source-level quality and secure use of frameworks. Compiler and platform teams are responsible for transformation integrity and reporting. Operators are responsible for deployment baselines, telemetry, and incident handling. Governance teams are responsible for policy, compliance, and exception management.

B. Add Gates Before Compilation and Backend Execution

Security gates should be placed before irreversible or costly transitions in the lifecycle. Before compilation, the pipeline should check source code, dependencies, secrets, configuration, and quantum-specific patterns. Before backend execution, it should verify emulator-based validation, target authorisation, evidence completeness, and policy or data-boundary constraints.

This avoids sending code to a simulator, cloud backend, or distributed test environment before the security context is known. A gate should not merely block or allow. It should produce a decision record explaining why the action was permitted, denied, or allowed under exception.

C. Build Evidence Stores, Not Only Dashboards

Dashboards show the current state of a pipeline or deployment, but they do not preserve the decision path. Quantum software teams should therefore design evidence storage as a

core platform function. The evidence store should index artefacts from planning, development, build, compilation, testing, release, deployment, operation, and monitoring.

It should support access control, redaction, search, policy evaluation, compliance snapshots, and audit export. Evidence should remain linked to the release or deployment it supports. Otherwise, a team may know that a control once ran, but not whether it applied to the artefact currently in operation.

D. Separate Research Mode from Release-Candidate Mode

Quantum software development often starts in exploratory settings where rapid iteration is necessary. The pipeline should therefore distinguish research mode from release-candidate mode. Research mode may permit flexible experimentation, incomplete evidence, and fast emulator-based testing.

Release-candidate mode should enforce complete evidence packages, reproducible configurations, baseline comparisons where relevant, signed artefacts, policy decisions, and explicit approval. This separation allows experimentation without weakening the discipline required for controlled deployment in medical, energy, and other sensitive domains.

E. Make Compliance Machine-Readable

Compliance should not depend only on manual document review. A quantum DevSecOps pipeline should translate relevant requirements into machine-readable policies for required evidence, mandatory checks, signing rules, deployment constraints, exception conditions, and monitoring obligations.

Machine-readable compliance does not eliminate human judgement. It makes routine decisions consistent and reviewable, while human review remains necessary for risk acceptance, exceptions, ambiguous requirements, and domain-specific judgement.

F. Avoid Unsupported Trust Claims

Terms such as “secure”, “compliant”, “quantum-safe”, and “trustworthy” should be used carefully. A stronger practice is to state what has been assured, including which code version was analysed, which dependencies were recorded, which compiler report was produced, which tests ran, which policy gate passed, which package was signed, which environment was verified, and which runtime signals are monitored.

This precision reduces ambiguity and protects organisations from overclaiming. Quantum software assurance is still developing, and trust claims should remain proportional to the evidence available.

G. Open Challenges

Several challenges remain unresolved. First, quantum software vulnerability taxonomies are still immature. The community lacks stable categories that cover unsafe circuit construction, insecure hybrid orchestration, backend misuse, quantum machine-learning weaknesses, and compiler-related risks. Second, benchmarks and datasets for evaluating quantum-aware security tools are limited. This makes it difficult to compare

scanners, LLM-assisted review tools, anomaly detectors, or secure compilation methods.

A related gap concerns regulatory and compliance methodology. Existing cybersecurity and digital regulations can apply to quantum software when it is delivered as a product, embedded in an AI system, used in critical infrastructure, or involved in personal-data processing. However, they do not yet provide mature operational methods for assessing quantum-specific artefacts. There is no widely adopted compliance methodology for quantum software pipelines, no stable taxonomy for quantum software vulnerabilities, and no common evidence schema for compiler reports, circuit provenance, backend assumptions, QBOMs, or distributed IoQT traces. Organisations may therefore identify high-level obligations while still lacking practical criteria for deciding whether a quantum workflow is ready for release, deployment, certification, or audit.

Third, evidence formats require further standardisation. SBOMs are already familiar in conventional software, but quantum-specific artefacts such as QBOMs, compiler security reports, circuit provenance, backend assumptions, and IoQT traces need clearer schemas. Fourth, tool interoperability remains difficult. Quantum ecosystems involve multiple programming frameworks, compilers, simulators, cloud providers, and execution models. Security tools must interoperate across these boundaries.

Finally, regulatory interpretation will evolve. Quantum software may fall under different obligations depending on whether it is an open-source component, a product with digital elements, part of an AI system, a medical workflow, or a critical-infrastructure tool. Quantum DevSecOps cannot remove this complexity, but it can provide the evidence needed to reason about it.

VII. CONCLUSION

Quantum computing changes more than the cryptographic threat model. It also introduces a software assurance problem. Quantum applications are built through hybrid workflows that combine classical code, quantum circuits, compilers, simulators, cloud backends, machine-learning components, distributed execution environments, and operational controls. Securing such systems requires more than post-quantum cryptographic migration and more than conventional DevSecOps applied unchanged.

A Quantum DevSecOps approach provides a practical direction for closing this gap. It treats quantum software as a lifecycle assurance problem, where trust is built through secure coding, quantum-aware compilation, emulator-first testing, policy-based gates, controlled deployment, runtime monitoring, and evidence generation. The SecQDevOps reference architecture illustrates how these capabilities can be integrated around secure development, hardware-aware compilation, Quantum MLOps, AI-driven security services, IoQT testing, compliance, certification, and pipeline evidence.

The central requirement is evidence. A quantum software release should not be trusted only because it executes successfully or because a dashboard reports no active alerts. It should be trusted because the relevant artefacts can be inspected,

including source versions, dependencies, quantum artefacts, compiler reports, test results, compliance decisions, signed packages, deployment manifests, telemetry, incident records, and drift reports. These artefacts make security claims specific, reproducible, and auditable.

The quantum ecosystem is still early enough for such practices to be built in rather than retrofitted later. If secure engineering remains secondary to experimentation, informal habits may become embedded in future quantum software stacks. If assurance, evidence, and accountability are integrated now, quantum software can mature with stronger foundations. The goal is not to slow quantum innovation, but to ensure that innovation can be deployed, reviewed, and trusted when it moves beyond the laboratory.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Funded by the European Union (GA 101225776 — SecQdevOps). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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